

A Reproducibility Study on *Simple and Efficient Recommendation Strategy for Warm/Cold Sessions for RecSys Challenge 2022*

MAX KLEINEGGER*, CLARA PICHLER*, PAUL SCHMITT*, and MARTIN WUSTINGER*, Technical University of Vienna, Austria

This paper presents our investigation to reproduce the results of a RecSys 2022 Challenge paper that addresses predicting user purchases in fashion e-commerce sessions. The original work introduces a sequence-aware MLP and a novel similarity metric to handle challenges like limited previous views and new item appearances. As we navigate through provided code and data challenges, coupled with uncertainties in the paper's methodology, we aim to shed light on the reproducibility of the original results. This paper outlines our efforts in looking into the experimental setup and results, aiming to validate or question the reported outcomes.

CCS Concepts: • **Information systems** → **Recommender systems**.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Recommender Systems, RecSys Challenge 2022, Session-based Recommendation, Cold-Start Problem, Experimental Design, Reproduction of Results

ACM Reference Format:

Max Kleinegger, Clara Pichler, Paul Schmitt, and Martin Wustinger. 2024. A Reproducibility Study on *Simple and Efficient Recommendation Strategy for Warm/Cold Sessions for RecSys Challenge 2022*. 1, 1 (February 2024), 6 pages. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10615787>

1 INTRODUCTION

The objective of the second assignment for the lecture *Experimental Design for Data Science*, is to provide a good understanding of the recreation of the experimental setup, experiments, and results as explained in a scientific paper. Reproducing scientific results is important for verifying the accuracy and trustworthiness of the findings presented in papers. This study aims to confirm the reliability of the results or identify discrepancies that may call their conclusions into question.

Recommender systems play an important role nowadays because they enhance user experience, offering personalized suggestions that make it easier for individuals to discover and choose items online, contributing to increased satisfaction and engagement in various domains. The paper *Simple and Efficient Recommendation Strategy for Warm/Cold Sessions for RecSys Challenge 2022* [1] which our group has chosen for reproducing aims to forecast the next item purchased based on a sequence of viewed items. The proposed approaches by the authors of the paper include a robust Sequence-Aware MLP (SMLP) for effective session-based recommendations, and a Popularity-Aware Cosine Similarity (PCos) to handle item trend shifts. SMLP excels in capturing sequence information crucial for session-based recommendation, boasting superior performance and faster inference. PCos addresses item trend shifts by distinguishing between cold and warm sessions, applying tailored recommendation strategies. In this context, cold sessions are sessions where most items in the view sequences do not appear in the training dataset. The evaluation metric which was used for this project is the Mean Reciprocal Rank given 100 items (MRR@100). These strategies prove pivotal in the dynamic fashion domain, where product trends change rapidly, ensuring the model's adaptability to emerging and vanishing items.

Although information and resources on this project are given, reproducing the performance results stated in the paper are very hard to reproduce, if one wants to do it correctly.

*All authors contributed equally to this research.

Authors' address: Max Kleinegger, e12041500@student.tuwien.ac.at; Clara Pichler, e11917694@student.tuwien.ac.at; Paul Schmitt, e11714338@student.tuwien.ac.at; Martin Wustinger, e12122402@student.tuwien.ac.at, Technical University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria, 1040.

2 EXPERIMENT SETUP

This section aims to illustrate how the reproducibility study was conducted, all issues and difficulties we encountered are listed in the next section and are only briefly mentioned here. Concerning our starting point, the authors of the paper provided a GitHub repository¹ containing the final code that was used for the submission during the challenge. Additionally, the full dataset² of the challenge is still accessible on the Dressipi webpage. The GitHub repository includes multiple README.md files, offering detailed guidance on executing scripts, training, and evaluating within the project, serving as a valuable starting point for our research.

2.1 Environment Setting and Requirements

The first challenge we had to overcome was the setup of the environment, in which all the scripts were supposed to run in. The paper was written in the year 2022 and therefore relies on somewhat outdated software. To complicate the situation even further, the scripts are set to run within a PyTorch/CUDA environment, which required the existence of a NVIDIA graphics card. To solve this issue we reached out to the Institute of Experiment Design, which provided us with access to a GPU server, which had NVIDIA cards installed. However, the server had some preinstalled versions of software, we were not able, or allowed, to downgrade. Hence, the following versions were used in comparison to the paper:

Software	Paper	Reproducing
Ubuntu	18.04	20.04
Python	3.9.1	3.9.18
CUDA	11.3	11.3
torch	1.11.0	1.11.0

2.2 Preprocessing and Data Preparation

In regards to data handling, the provided scripts work with relative paths and require the .csv files to be located in specific folders within the GitHub repository folder structure. However, due to some limitations with our access to the GPU server, we had to store our data on a mounted hard disk and were not able to leave them within the repository folder on the home partition. Therefore, we had to replace all hard coded relative paths to our own paths, as the project does not provide a uniform way to select such a partition. With all folder paths setup correctly we next stumbled onto some issues within the preprocessing.py script, that should theoretically setup all the data files required by the models. A detailed description on which errors occurred and how we solved them is described in Section 3.3.

2.3 Deviations between Code and Paper

With all data files in the required folders, the next step was to train the models, specified in the paper, and compare our results. First of all, it is a bit unclear which python script or folder corresponds to which of the mentioned models within the paper. While there were dedicated folders for the BERT4Rec and MLP models, each equipped with a unique README.md file explaining the setup and training process, such a folder was missing for the mentioned GRU4Rec model. However, after some digging we found some GRU models within the folder dedicated to the ensemble, namely a GRU, GNN and GRUN model. Interestingly, the name GRU4Rec was never even mentioned in the GitHub. Additionally, we found another MLP model within the ensemble folder, which was according to our knowledge not required, and was replaced by the model in the dedicated folder.

¹<https://github.com/kakao/kakao-recoteam-recsys-2022-challenge>

²<https://dressipi.com/downloads/recsys-datasets/>

2.4 Model Training

This left us with a total of three separate models that we could train and compare with the paper, BERT4Rec, MLP and the Ensemble, containing the GRU models and PCos. First of all it should be mentioned, that all the the model training procedures store their results in `.logits` files, which are later used by the ensemble to compute the final model. The setup and training procedures for the BERT4Rec and MLP models worked pretty much as provided, with the only required alterations being the changes to the file paths. Also the GRU, GNN and GRUN models had to be trained separately before starting the ensemble. However, this time the repository opted to training each model 20 times, each iteration with a different seed, and in a later step picking the 10 best models from each type. This procedure was especially computational expensive which is why we had to split the work between multiple GPUs to compute in parallel.

After the training of each of the individual models, we could finally start the training of the ensemble. Where no new problems or incidents occurred.

3 DIFFICULTIES

This section describes all the difficulties and problems we encountered while trying to reproduce the paper. It explains the problems we faced during setting up the environmental setup, problems that encountered during data generation and generally problems with the code base. The tables below sum up which of the different types of difficulties we have encountered, where the check mark indicates that it was indeed a problem for us.

Code not provided	X	Data not provided	X
Code partially not provided	✓	Data partially not provided	✓
Faulty code provided	✓	Results differ drastically	✓
Information about software versions missing	✓	Comparison metrics or baselines not discussed	✓
Specific hardware and software setup necessary	✓	Experimental setup not described	X
Inconsistencies in paper, code and data	✓	Experiment workflow incomplete	✓

3.1 Inconsistencies between Paper and Code

Before we describe in a more detailed manor which problems and errors we encountered, we want to highlight some major inconsistencies between the paper and the code, most likely originating from the fact that the paper was written before the final submission of the challenge. However, the absence of any commit history or documentation makes it rather difficult to reconstruct the path the authors went when writing the paper.

First and foremost, the paper lies a heavy emphasis on the distinction between Cold and Warm sessions, with the difference being how long products have been available at the time of the session. However, this emphasis is completely neglected within the code, which never even mentions a way to distinguish the two types, moreover providing a way to split the dataset accordingly. Therefore making it impossible to identify where the MRR@100 scores, stated in the paper, are coming from or how they can be recreated.

Additionally, as also already mentioned in the previous section, some models mentioned in the paper, are only present in a slightly modified version in the code. Especially the GRU4Rec and PCos classifiers have dedicated scores stated in the paper and are only present as components to the ensemble in the code. Making it again impossible to recompute those scores without any major changes or additions to the code.

3.2 Environment Setting

The authors provided through the paper and source code their experimental setup. They mentioned their operation systems as well as the versions of the main libraries (i.e. torch) used to conduct the experiment. Furthermore,

they specified additional versions of GCC to get everything up and running. The first difficulties arose during the installation of all packages because they did not specify any version used for other libraries. This led to the problem that the source code would not start because of deprecated versions. For this reason, the installation of every torch library (torch, torch-geometric, torch-lightning) was rather frustrating and quite difficult because one had to look up compatible versions, and we cannot guarantee that those are the same as they used. As already mentioned in Section 2.1, the dependency on torch+cuda complicates or potentially precludes reproduction efforts for those lacking the appropriate infrastructure, for that reason, we relied on the access to the GPU servers provided by TU Vienna.

Addressing the mentioned issues is relatively straightforward in comparison to the more significant challenges associated with the paper and its source code concerning the experimental setup. The source code shared for the challenge’s final submission differs from the one specifically used for the metrics outlined in the paper. This, coupled with varying approaches detailed in multiple README.md files, makes replicating the paper incredibly hard. Therefore, reproducing the paper relies on the best efforts of those attempting it, as there is no guarantee that the authors followed the same procedures. More precisely, this means you do not know if they executed the same files in the same order, because two README.md files differ in a small portion. The suggested course of action by those files differs from the described method in the paper.

3.3 Data

The provided data remains accessible as of January 31, 2024, with one README.md file detailing the preprocessing steps and relevant files. The paper also explains the calculation of their scores, though the methodologies suggested in the paper and README.md diverge. The dataset spans two years containing one million sessions from January 2020 to May 2021. Within the challenge context, multiple test sets exist, including a leaderboard set and a final test set, likely released post-deadline. Notably, the paper’s reported scores derive from an internal test set, detailed only textually, employing data from the last three months and omitting older observations. The split for internal testing, covering March, April, and a randomly sampled half of May’s observations for training, with the remaining May observations for testing, lacks mention in the README or the repository. We replicated this specific split using a modified notebook from the repository, guided by the paper’s description rather than the README instructions. Adjustments were necessary in the preprocessing.py script to bypass automatic split generation and incorporate our data version. Running preprocessing.py with the submit flag set to false, intended for internal train-test use, initially caused errors, resolved by minor bug fixes.

The issue with the submit-flag persists throughout the project, causing errors and complications in various components. This problem likely arises from the project’s design, which prioritizes a codebase optimized for challenge submission over one suited for reproduction.

Description	Paper	Reproducing
Number of items	23691	23691
Number of categories	904	904
Avg. categories of an item	19.47	19.91
Avg. session length	4.74	4.74

3.4 Code

With the data finally ready, we followed the experimental setup to execute the experiment. This did not work out of the box. The reasons for that are small typos, faulty code, or bugs in the code. Those problems were fixed rather quickly and easily. A bigger problem was that none of the actual code was documented. Therefore we

had to assume what parameters did, based on the code it executed. The problem with this is that there are some portions of the code one cannot fully understand without deeper documentation or knowledge of the authors. After fixing and reverse-engineering everything to the best knowledge, we could finally run the experiment and get some results.

4 RESULTS

This section compares and analyzes the results we got from reproducing the paper. With our setup in place and everything running smoothly, we have encountered a significant problem in our reproducibility study. The source code the authors provided was used for generating the results for the final submission for the challenge. Therefore, it should run and return the wanted results as expected. However, we came to the conclusion that to fully reproduce all of the metrics which were calculated in the paper, source code or at least some sort of documentation is missing. That is why, although our aim was to reproduce the three last tables from their report [1], we only managed to reproduce single values from Table 4, which states the MRR@100 results using different models. Since the code for the MRR@100 results using Cold Session Classifier (CSC) was also not available for us we can only compare their results on the model-only column.

Model	Paper	Reproducing
Bert4Rec	0.1756	0.2558
SMLP	0.1913	0.1925
Ensemble	0.1974	0.2995

The results we received are not really giving us any useful information, since those few values are simply not enough for a detailed analysis. However, it would not have been possible with the information provided to reproduce more values that we could have compared to the performance results stated in the paper.

For Table 2 and Table 3 from [1], we did not have the same code, as the authors, to evaluate the metrics. Even though for Table 3 the source code contained parameters, that could suggest evaluating the different cases, without proper documentation and the problem that only one model contains such parameters, it is not reproducible. In comparison, the source code, which could lead to results from Table 2 was completely missing, preventing us from reproducing any further metrics.

Although our very few results are quite similar, the reason why we did not get the same results is probably a mix of many factors, already starting with the data used. Therefore, statistically testing would not make a lot of sense since it still would not give us any more information.

5 CONCLUSION

After investing a lot of time and effort into the given project, and believing in the reproducibility of the paper, we unfortunately were not able to reproduce their results as intended. The main reason behind this was the poor documentation and missing parts of the code. In general, challenges usually have strict deadlines, putting pressure on participants to finish and share their work quickly. This urgency can lead to issues like incomplete or potentially unoptimized code, making it close to impossible to reproduce any results without a good understanding and programming knowledge. Since the primary focus is on ensuring the success of the final submission, and the importance of prior testing is somewhat diminished, it is simply lacking the necessary components for reproducing the metrics stated in the paper. Moreover, the rush to meet deadlines may result in not enough documentation. In such cases, decoding the code nuances, understanding the experimental design, and ensuring reliable results become complex tasks as one can see with our efforts.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Lee, S. Yoo, A. Yang, W. Jang, and C. Park. Simple and efficient recommendation strategy for warm/cold sessions for recsys challenge 2022. In *Proceedings of the Recommender Systems Challenge 2022*, RecSysChallenge '22, page 50–54, New York, NY, USA, 2022. Association for Computing Machinery.

Received 28 January 2024